

Ahrorova Feruza Hamza qizi

Master's student of the specialty of Ethnography, ethnology and anthropology,
Samarkand State University named after Sharof Rashidov

Abstract: Archaeological research and the main archaeological monuments of Karmana, archaeological research was carried out at the Burqutepa, Chillatepa, Old Mound, Kaltepa and Kunjaktepa monuments located in the district. During the research, many monuments of ancient and early medieval times were recorded in this area, and this article discusses the latest archaeological research in the Karmana district and their results.

Keywords: Central Asia, Karmana, Kyzylkum, Zarafshan, early Middle Ages, Middle Ages, defensive wall, ark, shahristan, rabod.

Introduction. Archaeological research conducted in the Karmana district in recent years has yielded important results in the scientific study of the rich history of this region and the identification of historical and cultural layers. As a result of excavations conducted at monuments such as Burqutepa, Chillatepa, Old Kurgan, Kaltepa and Kunjaktepa, numerous archaeological finds, architectural remains and cultural layers dating back to the ancient and early medieval periods were discovered. The materials obtained from these monuments make the Karmana region an important source not only for the archeology of Uzbekistan, but also for the entire Central Asia. This article scientifically analyzes the etymology of the name Karmana, its geographical location, its reflection in historical sources and the results of recent archaeological research conducted in the region. This sheds light on the place of the Karmana region in ancient and medieval history, urbanization processes, the interaction of urban and rural life, stages of cultural development and the scientific significance of archaeological monuments.

Literature review. The name Karmana was first mentioned in 712 in the work of the historian Abu Ja'far Muhammad ibn Jarir at-Tabari, "Tarihi ar-rusul wal-muluk" ("History of the Prophets and Rulers") (Abu Ja'far al-Tabari, 1987; 229). Later, information about Karmana is also found in the historical and geographical work "Hudud ul-Olam" (The Boundaries of the World), written by an unknown author in 983. The work mentions the geographical location of Karmana, its location on the Samarkand road from Bukhara, its prosperity, clean water, and abundance of various delicacies (Hudud ul-Olam. Bartolda, 1930; 22). In the work "History of Bukhara" by the 10th century historian Muhammad Narshahi, Karmana is described as follows: Karmina is one of the villages of Bukhara, its water comes from the Bukhara water: its khiroji is added to the

khiroji of Bukhara. It also has its own separate village; a mosque and a mosque were built there. There were many writers and poets in Karmina (Narshahi, 1991; 95).

In addition, the name Karmina is mentioned in Ibn Arabshah's "History of Amir Timur", Mirzo Ulugbek's "History of the Four Nations", Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi's "Zafarnoma", Mirzo Babur's "Boburnoma", Abu Tahirhoja Samarkandi's "Samaria", Mir Muhammad Amin Bukhari's "Ubaydullanoma" and many other works. The occurrence of this name in the works of famous scientists and writers indicates the high status of Karmina.

One of the oldest monuments located in the Karmina region is the Burquttepa monument. The first brief information about this monument was left by A.Y. Yakubovsky, the head of the Zarafshan expedition in 1934. According to him, the monument consisted of an ark (kohandiz), a shahristan and a rabad (Yakubovsky, 1934; 150). In 1986, a schematic plan of the monument was drawn up, and based on fragments of archaeological finds excavated from it, it was assumed that people lived in Burkuttepa from the 3rd-2nd centuries BC to the Middle Ages (Manylov, 1987; 171-173).

Main part. As a result of archaeological research conducted at the Burquttepa monument in 1999-2001, an 8-meter-wide defensive wall of the arch was uncovered and studied, and at the same time, as a result of excavations carried out in the northern part of the arch, the remains of a basement-like dwelling were discovered here, along with archaeological finds of the monument dating back to the 4th-3rd centuries BC. The monument is located 150-200 meters east of the Shahristan arch (now converted into a cemetery), and as a result of excavations conducted here during the last field season, numerous pottery fragments, baked bricks, and millstones dating back to the 10th and 13th centuries were recorded (Khujanazarov, Mirzaakhmedov, Gritsina, Rakhimov. 2001. 189-190; Khujanazarov, Gritsina, Mirzaakhmedov. 2002; 179-186). A scientific analysis of the findings obtained as a result of research conducted in Shahristan in 2023 shows that people lived here not only in the Middle Ages, but also in the early Middle Ages, that is, in the 5th-8th centuries, and taking into account the fact that a cultural layer continues here, we can assume that the ark and Shahristan appeared at the same time.

The Old Kurgan monument is located on the left bank of the Zarafshan River, which is now completely destroyed and replaced by residential areas. Glazed pottery fragments recovered from this area date from the 15th to the early 20th centuries. The pottery materials were divided into four groups: 1) 15th-16th centuries; 2) late 17th-mid 18th centuries; 3) second half of the 18th century-mid 19th century; 4) second half of the 19th century-early 20th century (Gritsina, Mirzaakhmedov, Khozhanazarov. 2000; 73-75). In 2022-2023, in order to determine the area of the rabad part of the Burquttepa monument, excavations were carried out in several pits approximately 20 meters south and east of

the arch, as well as in its city center. In the layers excavated in the pits, fragments of pottery vessels from different periods were recorded, and it was determined that this place consists of mixed layers. As can be seen from this data, the rabod part was fully developed during the construction works carried out in the territory of the city of Karmana since the late Middle Ages. In addition, archaeological excavations were carried out in the monuments of rural settlements (Chillatepa, Kunjaktepa) located in the areas close to the Burquttepa monument, as well as field research studies were carried out to form a list of archaeological monuments of the district.

The main goal of studying the rural areas located in the outskirts of the city of Karmana was to determine the relationship between the city and the countryside. In particular, excavations were carried out in a trench measuring 2.8x7.5 m from the southern edge of the Chillatepa monument arch and an area measuring 3x5.5 m and 2.5x3.75 m on the southern border of its settlement. As a result of the research, material cultures from the period from antiquity to the 12th century were identified in the trench in the palace area. According to preliminary data, the settlement was formed in late antiquity, and the remains of a defensive wall built of mud brick dating back to the early Middle Ages were discovered and studied on the cultural layers of this period. The defensive wall was built of mud brick measuring 42x23x9 cm, with a preservation height of 1 m and a width of 1.85 m. The pottery vessels found around this wall were determined to date back to the 7th-8th centuries AD. The village, which fell into crisis in the early Middle Ages, was redeveloped during the Karakhanid period in the 11th-12th centuries. In particular, among the upper layers, baked bricks and fragments of pottery vessels dating back to this period were observed (Saidov, Rakhimov, Kholmatov, Khozhamov, Omonov, 2023; 40). Researchers have expressed their opinions about this monument as a defensive wall of the early Middle Ages of the city (Rahimov, Raimkulov. 2024; 193-196).

In addition, research was carried out at the Kunjaktepa monument on the outskirts of the city, and a 2x11.5 m trench was excavated in its north-western side and a 2x3 m pit 8 meters from the western side of the monument. In the trench excavated in the north-western area of the monument, the remains of 4 pakhsa and mudbrick defensive walls dating back to the early medieval period and the remains of a pakhsa-walled dwelling on its inner side were discovered. In one of the rooms, the remains of 2 side-by-side household pits were discovered. One of these pits was built on the floor of the room, while the other was cut off from the floor of the room, and the depth of its preserved part reaches 20 cm. During these excavations, fragments of a goblet, a red-glazed bowl, and a date pot dating back to the late antiquity period were found between the defensive wall (Saidov, Rakhimov, Kholmatov, Khozhamov, Omonov, 2023; 40). The Kaltepa monument was

studied by the Navoi archaeological detachment in 1986. The topography was drawn, photographed, and described. According to it, the monument is rectangular in shape, measuring 60x54 m. The northern part is 4.5 m high. Most of it is covered with a cemetery. The pottery fragments found during the excavations date back to the antique and early medieval periods. From the results of the research, it can be concluded that the Kaltepa archaeological monument is the remains of a small settlement belonging to the rural nobility in its time.

Conclusion. Although the territory of the Chillatepa monument occupied a large area in antiquity and the early Middle Ages, the discovery of a defensive wall here indicates that the monument had a smaller area in the 7th-8th centuries. The Chillatepa village, which experienced a crisis in the early Middle Ages, was redeveloped during the Karakhanid period in the 11th-12th centuries. This is evidenced by the fragments of baked bricks and pottery vessels belonging to this period among the upper layers of the monument.

During the excavations carried out at the Kunjaktepa monument, the discovery of a goblet, a red-glazed bowl, and fragments of a date pot belonging to the late antiquity period among the defensive wall proves that the lower layers of the monument belong to this period, that is, to the late antiquity period.

The pottery vessels found in the rural areas, with their high quality of preparation technique and technology, are not inferior to the pottery vessels from the Burkuttepa monument, the site of the oldest city of Karmana, that is, they were made by city craftsmen.

According to preliminary data, 46 monuments have been registered in the Karmana district, and the lack of sufficient research in the district and the recording of rock carvings in this area require the systematic continuation of archaeological research in this area in the coming years, and at the same time, such research will create an opportunity to shed more light on the history of the district in a more accurate and detailed way.

References

1. Abu Ja'far Tabari. History of Tabari (Istoriya al-Tabari). Predislovie i primechaniya V. I. Belyaeva. - T., 1987.
2. Gritsina A.A, Mirzaakhmedov D.K., Khojanazarov M. Pozdnesrednevekovaya keramik s Gorodishcha Kukhan Kurgan // "Archaeology, Numismatics and epigraphy srednevekovoy Sredney Azii. Samarkand. 2000.
3. Manylov Yu.P. Otchet o rabotakh v Navoiyskoy oblasti po teme: Sostavlenie karty archeolot-icheskih pamyatnikov Navoiyskoy oblasti v 1986 g. // Archive IA AN Uzbekistan. Samarkand, 1987.
4. Narshakhi M. History of Bukhara. "Heritage" series. - T., 1991.

5. Rahimov K.A., Raimkulov A.A. Chillatepa monument-defensive wall of the early Middle Ages // Bulletin of Khorezm Ma'mun Academy. Khiva-2024. No. 6/3.
6. Saidov M.M., Rakhimov K.A., Kholmatov A.N., Khojamov S.H., Omonov D.S. archaeological research // Socio-economic, political history, material and spiritual culture of the peoples of Central Asia (from ancient times to the present day) (materials of the republican scientific and practical conference) Samarkand 2023.
7. Khozhayazarov M., Mirzaakhmedov D.K., Gritsina A.A., Rakhimov K.A.. Archaeological work carried out in Karmana and its surroundings // Archaeological research in Uzbekistan in 2000. Samarkand. 2001.
8. Khudud ul-Olam. Manuscript by Tumansky. With an introduction and indexes by Bartold. - Leningrad, 1930.
9. Yakubovsky A.Yu. Archaeological expedition to the Zarafshan valley in 1934 // Proceedings of the Department of History of Culture and Art of the East. Vol. U. Leningrad, 1940.